

EDİTÖRE MEKTUP

LETTER TO EDITOR

ANESTHESIA MANAGEMENT IN HYDATID CYST SURGERY

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ABSTRACT

Hydatid cyst is a parasitic disease transmitted through dog feces, caused by Echinococcus granulosus in countries with agriculture and animal husbandry. Proper anesthesia management is critical to minimize the risk of anaphylaxis during surgery for hydatid disease. To minimize the risk, the anesthetist should administer appropriate prophylactic medications and closely monitor the patient for any suspicious symptoms, such as hemodynamic instability.

Keywords: Anaphylaxis, Bronchospasm, Hydatid cyst

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Dear Editor,

We read the study titled 'New Diagnosis of Hepatic Hydatid Cyst Presenting with Dyspnea' and found its contribution to the literature important (1). Given the specific characteristics of hydatid disease and its requirement for surgical intervention, proper anesthesia management and approach during the perioperative period become crucial factors in minimizing the risk of anaphylaxis. Although the frequency of intraoperative anaphylactic reactions is rare (1/6,000 – 1/20,000), the mortality rate is between 3-6% (2). The incidence of intraoperative anaphylaxis caused by hydatid cysts is reported to be between 2% and 3.3%, which is a significant concern for anesthesiologists (3).

During cyst excision in the perioperative period, symptoms may vary from mild allergic reactions to anaphylactic shock. Prophylactic application of steroids and H1 receptor blockers at the beginning of surgery prevents mediator release from basophils and stabilizes mast cells (4). Corticosteroids can prevent recurrence of anaphylactic reaction symptoms and reduce life-threatening airway edema (5).

Anaphylactic reactions during anesthesia may manifest themselves through various symptoms, including hypotension caused by hemodynamic instability, sudden decline in peripheral oxygen saturation due to bronchospasm, and the development of urticaria (6).

The development of an Ig E-mediated anaphylactic reaction is triggered by the high antigenic content present in the cyst fluid upon its entry into the systemic circulation. In order to achieve the desired therapeutic outcome, it is essential to ensure optimal levels of vascular tone, intravascular volume, and cardiac output. Therefore, the primary objective of treatment is to maintain and monitor these physiological parameters, thereby promoting overall vascular stability and homeostasis (7).

The prompt initiation of early aggressive treatment is of utmost significance. It is recommended to elevate the oxygen level to 100% and to promptly administer intravenous colloid or crystalloid fluids, adrenaline, and steroids. This approach can potentially avert unfavorable outcomes and ensure optimal patient outcomes (7).

Adrenaline is the most appropriate drug for treating bronchospasm and massive peripheral vasodilation. Depending on the severity of the reaction, long-term infusion may be required (8).

Extubation should not be performed immediately in a patient with an intraoperative anaphylactoid reaction as inflammation continues and airway edema occurs (9). As such, it is essential to closely monitor the patient in the intensive care unit during the postoperative period. In the context of hydatid cyst surgery, an anaphylactic reaction should be considered a possibility. To mitigate the risk, the anesthetist should administer appropriate prophylactic medications and monitor the patient closely for any signs of suspicious symptoms, such as hemodynamic instability, which should prompt urgent and aggressive treatment.

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